

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Demonstration plans for activities at DEMO SITES: User involvement

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LIST OF CHANGES ADDRESSING REVIEWER'S COMMENTS

Comment	Change	Section, page
A description of the “business as usual” is missing illustrating the current value chains	The BAU and the current linear value chains have been added to the document. More elaborative description of these value chains and key challenges can be found in D8.3	Sections 4.1.1, 4.2.1 and 4.3.1 have been added to the document
A description of the modified circular business case perspective for the planned demos is also missing	Circular value chains representing the circular set up at the system level for each industrial sector have been added to the document. Also, the approach for developing the value chains have been explained as well.	Sections 4.1.3, 4.2.3 and 4.3.3 have been added to the document. Also Section 3 has been extended to explain how the circular value chains have been developed
The breakdown of activities in 4.1 and responsibilities at point 2 in Table 2 are sound though the activities breakdown is not consistent with the responsibilities breakdown (e.g.who is responsible for EOL recovery test?). What is missing, is the sequencing of the activities to form a Gantt chart with milestones.	Responsibilities for demo activities (including EoL tests) have been clarified by developing the demo maps and updating the logistics tables	Demo maps in Sections 4.1.3, 4.2.3 and 4.3.3 have been added to the document. Also, Sections 4.1.4, 4.2.4 and 4.3.4 provides more updated demo plans with clear responsibilities and timelines
In the description of activities in §4.1.2, demonstration is partially mixed with dissemination/communication. For instance, the question about “exhibitions” points more to communication/ than demonstration and so does the reply about ECOMONDO	This comment no longer applies since Section 4.1.2 has been changed	Please see Section 4.1.4 for updated demonstration plans for automotive sector
It is not clear if the reverse logistics will be demonstrated or not?	Reverse logistics will be demonstrated in the furniture sector where Moretti will be testing leasing business model. Also, labelling and tracking system will be tested in the construction sector for components manufactured by Conenor	Demo maps in Sections 4.1.3, 4.2.3 and 4.3.3 have been added to the document

Executive Summary

This report presents planned activities with end users on demonstrating ECOBULK circular solutions and how to contribute to “closing the loop” of composite products in three sectors; automotive, furniture and building by promoting greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products, parts, and materials.

During the period M12-M18 a common dialogue between the partners involved in demonstrations has been initiated in order to understand and establish the interactions between them for successful planning and outcome of the demonstration activities while understanding that the design process is iterative, with many cycles of prototyping, testing, analysing and refining a product and finally designing the user application in away to benefit of the properties and sustainability they provide. This dialogue has resulted an initial plan reported in M18 for several highly interesting large-scale demonstrations to become carried out all over Europe within this project.

Following the feedback received during the M18 project review meeting in Brussel, the project demonstrators have been reconsidered by taking the system approach and merging all elements of the circular economy set up that is being developed in ECOBULK (e.g. business models, end of life, take back systems, digital systems, etc.). The outcome of this work was the development of demonstration maps for all three sectors (furniture, construction and automotive), consisting of several demo activities at each stage of the circular value chain, and a list of partners involved in these demo activities. The maps are supported with the demo cards that summarise the baseline situation and the project value-added innovation enhancing circularity at each stage of the circular value chain.

The demo plans presented in M18 have been also updated with a more specific breakdown of demo activities, a list of key responsibilities for each demo site, logistics information and specific timelines for demos execution. It is important to note though that the demo plans and timelines shall not be considered as definite and could be subject to revision during their execution upon timely plans requested by demo sites owners some being third parties. This report is a live document which will be regularly updated as the demo activities advances.

The next steps involve the coordination of the manufacturing processes with OEMs and the administrative procedures with the demo owners to make sure that the demo products are successfully deployed within the schedule. Also, the progress in other demo activities reported in the demo maps and cards will be monitored closely with responsible partners to ensure smooth execution and implementation of the demo plans. Any deviations from the predefined schedule will be regularly updated and contingency measures proposed.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description and purpose of the deliverable

This document presents the planned activities with end users on demonstrating ECOBULK circular solutions and how to contribute to “closing the loop” of composite products in three sectors; automotive, furniture and construction by promoting greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products, parts, and materials.

The demonstration plan provides an outline of ECOBULK demonstration activities taking place all over the Europe during years 2019-2021. The report has been divided into two complementary versions, with the first version (submitted in M18) providing an overview of product designs that are being developed in ECOBULK, as well as application of these products into specific demo sites. The second version of the report (due in M24) follows the recommendations from M18 project review meeting and it provides a more comprehensive and holistic plan for project demonstrators, including (1) a breakdown of demonstrators into series of demo activities that together contribute to the creation of circular value chains in three targeted sectors; (2) updated pilot product designs; (3) updated demo plans specifying key activities, responsibilities and logistics information for each demo site; and (4) specific timelines for demo plans execution.

It is important to note that this report is a live document which will be regularly updated as the project advances.

1.2. Relevance

In the automotive sector new materials supporting sustainability and circularity of plastic composites will be having the main role in designing and manufacturing easy to replace and refurbish internal car parts by three demonstrators Maier in Spain, CRF in Italy and MicroCab in the UK.

New binder material developed by AkzoNobel will be used in manufacturing environmentally friendly wood panels and providing healthy living conditions by KEAS which will be used in indoor furniture designs produced by Moretti Compact and demonstrated in the UK, Portugal and Italy.

Conenor will produce weather resistant extruded composite components for outdoor benches and tables for demonstrations to local designs and user preferences in Finland, France, UK and Portugal from recycled plastics and waste wood fibres.

Building & construction products from composite waste materials will be manufactured by Conenor and using first time ever glass fibre reinforced thermoset plastic (GFRP) waste taken from End of Life wind turbine blades as well as other GFRP-manufacturing waste as reinforcement in extruded composite profiles and panels for structural applications like various type of shelters and cabins and other outdoor constructions. Those volume

demonstrations to pay attention and attract citizens to have a closer look will take place in the UK, Portugal, France and especially in Finland at the new MOTO GP track and sports adventure centre named KymiRing under construction to host their first world cup race in 2020.

Preferences at each individual demo site and end user involvement are key attributes in Ecobulk new product- and assembly design work to compare benefits vs. BAU in the new structures at user interface. EU- and national standards and (building) codes and good practices shall be monitored for their relevancy and followed when applicable and mandatory.

An important element of the work for “closing the loop” will be the assessment of re-manufacturing/recyclability of the circular designed components by their manufacturers.

2. Demonstration activities – background information

2.1. Overview of main sectors to be demonstrated

Demonstration of the circular design solutions in ECOBULK will focus on three large impact industrial sectors: automotive, furniture and construction. These three sectors were selected for application of the circular approach during the project proposal stage, and it is justified by the high numbers of synergies these sectors, for example, in terms of the design (design for modularity, design for disassembly/dismantling), materials (fibre and particle reinforced plastic composites), manufacturing technology (moulding, extrusion, hot pressing, thermobonding) and new business models (leasing, renting, fix-it shops, etc.).

The DoW foresees a separate Work Package (WP4) dedicated exclusively to the project demonstration activities and led by Conenor. The main three tasks in WP4 (one for each industrial sector) are presented in Table 1, together with leading partner and other participants in these tasks.

Task	Title	Leader	Participants
T4.1	DEMO 1: CAR INDUSTRY – Modular circular designed internal car parts	MAIER	CRF, Tecnar, NetComposite, NTT, UPC, MicroCab
T4.2	DEMO 2: FURNITURE INDUSTRY – Modular circular designed products	MORETTI	Conenor, KEAS, Technoplants, NTT, UPC, CNR, Lipor, FCBA
T4.3	DEMO 3: BUILDING COMPONENTS – Modular circular designed products	CONENOR	UPC, CNR, KEAS, Exergy, AkzoNobel, Technoplants, NTT, Lipor

Table 1 – Demonstration activities

Demonstration activities in the car industry are led by Maier, plastic components manufacturer for the automotive industry. Automotive interior components will be manufactured and validated in T4.1 demonstrating that the design considerations taken in WP2 to achieve modularity and product/part reuse, recovery and recycle are effective in terms of circularity and sustainability objectives. Task 4.2 is led by a furniture manufacturer Moretti Compact, objective of which is to manufacture final demonstrators for furniture taking into account circular design considerations in WP2 as well as materials developed in WP3. Finally, T4.3 led by Conenor (recycled composite materials & extrusion R&D company) aims at manufacturing final demonstrators for building components, and demonstrating them in various light construction and outdoor furniture applications, such as benches, rain and bike shelters, waste collection points, information signs and cabins, etc. A more detailed description of planned demonstration activities in ECOBULK will be presented in Section 4.

2.2. Initial considerations

An initial description for pilot products and demo sites for these products from the project proposal stage is drafted in the ECOBULK Grant Agreement. However, these preliminary considerations have been subject to revision since the start of the project and have been redefined for the following reasons:

- **Changes in product designs:** the design process in WP2 resulted in some changes in the concept ideas regarding the prototypes proposed during the proposal stage. For example, some of the pilot products in the construction sector (e.g. conventional fencing and decking systems built from commercial WPC-products existing in the market and available from dozens of manufacturers) were considered not ambitious enough to fully demonstrate the circular economy objectives set at the project proposal stage. The idea behind ECOBULK is to push the boundaries as much as possible by looking at more demanding and complex structural product systems at yet non-discovered potential new applications (e.g. shelters, information cabins, waste collection points, etc.), which enable to demonstrate more circular economy strategies and at the same do not cause too much of an additional regulatory and administrative burdens to the project.
- **New material developments:** new collaborative efforts resulted in formulation of new composite materials suitable for application previously not considered in the project. For example, an external collaboration between Conenor and Virol (wind turbine blade recycling company) resulted in cross-linked PEX-waste being replaced by wind turbine blade Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) waste. This is a first time ever when GFRP-waste is being recycled and used as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic

composites. This new weather resistant composite material is applicable to various outdoor furniture and structural construction applications. This also provides new commercial opportunities considering huge quantities of non-recyclable wind turbine blade waste foreseen in the coming years and that the net cost of obtaining GFRP-material coming from the wind turbine blades is negative and lacking a feasible and sustainable recycling solution. Moreover the same applies also to other industries, like e.g. EoL GFRP-boats & yachts, which may benefit from the outcome of these developments.

- **Expectations of the demo site owners (users):** new possible and applications and pilot products (particularly in the furniture and construction sectors) were also derived based on the discussion with potential users of these products in the project (demo site owners), including largest building and construction demo site owner KymiRing Motor Sports Centre in Finland. The main interest of, for example, KymiRing demo site, matching the Conenor's extruded composite capacities, was found in four targeted applications: outdoor benches for visitors, modular shelters against rain for visitors, info cabins for employees and info signs (replacing previously defined fencing, decking and temporary shelter products). In the indoor furniture sector, the design for circularity and user acceptance will be tested in several student accommodation within Coventry University. Also, business meeting rooms in Warwick University will be furnished with Ecobulk furniture to experiment the benefits of modular furniture depending on user necessities, providing the opportunity to rethink manufactures and universities business models.
- **Changes in demonstration sites:** new product designs and developments have brought motivation to seek new and more promising demo site opportunities where these new concepts could be deployed. For example, Exergy was able to engage two local Universities (Warwick University and Coventry University) to demonstrate pilot products in the furniture and construction sectors.
- **Changes in the consortium:** furniture company Formitalia, responsible for designing, manufacturing and demonstrating indoor furniture pilot products, has left the consortium and was replaced by a new furniture company Moretti Compact, taking over the duties and responsibilities from Formitalia in WP2 and WP4. This change resulted in new, previously not considered, furniture products that were to be designed and developed in the project (e.g. modular chairs, beds and desks).

The above-mentioned changes and advancements have brought new considerations regarding demonstration activities in the ECOBULK project. These new considerations were taken into account while working on the updated version of demonstration plans compared to the project proposal

stage. The next section demonstrates the logic and thought process used to develop new revised demonstration plans for the ECOBULK project.

3. Description of the demonstration plans definition process

A general approach was adopted to assess the demonstration activities as defined in the proposal stage and refine the process for the final definition of the demo sites and the demonstration plans.

The actual definition of the demonstration activities and thus the demonstration plans are ongoing processes based on the circular design strategies being implemented in WP2 and the discussions at the end-user interface. The general approach to re-define the demonstration plans could be summarized in the following 5 main steps:

- a) Understanding consortium capabilities;**
- b) Refining potential list of products/applications;**
- c) Identification and alignment of users and other stakeholders' needs;**
- d) Preliminary conceptual designs,**
- e) Iteration of conceptual designs with end-users for their feedback.**
- f) Developing demonstration maps for project demo activities
Developing more detailed demo plans together with specific timelines for their execution.**

During the period M12-M18 a common dialogue between the partners involved in demonstrations has been initiated in order to understand and establish the interactions between them for successful planning and outcome of the demonstration activities. As described in the general approach, those interactions have been facilitated by the following actions:

Identification of manufactures capabilities: Through a questionnaire, manufactures provided a list of specific products that could be targeted within the scope of ECOBULK Project. The preliminary product selection considered their current R&D activities, the potential for adopting the circular principles adopted in ECOBULK in terms of circular design, material fractions and alternative product shapes to be made available. The questionnaire for collecting information from each manufacture in the three sectors was can be found in Annex 1.

Design strategies and material choices: Along with the definition of capabilities, the collaboration with WP2 (design) and WP3 (materials) has sharpen the focus on what material fractions to use in product development by product manufacturers, what product shapes and designs to become materialised, and which product assemblies that are more suitable secure a meaningful and successful realization of the demonstration activities being planned.

Preliminary end-user feedback: Discussions and meeting have been held with demo site owners to communicate the project aims and share understanding of demo site owners’ needs and wishes and to reveal and overcome possible discrepancies. For this purpose, a questionnaire collecting the essential information for each demonstration site in the three sectors; automotive, furniture and building & construction was created, see Annex 1.

Preliminary conceptual designs: Following the discussion of capabilities, preliminary products ideas and user feedback, the consortium partners have been working on the conceptual designs for some of the products and applications. Details of the preliminary concepts were presented in D4.4 submitted in M18.

Iteration of conceptual designs with end-users: The product and application designs are ongoing processes and the results presented in M18 were subject to revision based on the feedback received from the end-users. The circular design strategy developed in WP2 encourage a collaborative design approach and hence subsequent iterations were carried out to finalize the designs and materialise the prototypes according to the time line presented in Figure 1, while observing the results obtained in materials’ developments in WP3. Updated prototype designs by M24 can be found in sections 4.1.2, 4.2.2 and 4.3.2.

ECOBULK PRODUCTS

ECOBULK SUPPORTING SYSTEMS AND ACTIVITIES

Figure 1 – ECOBULK project timeline

Development of demonstration maps for circularly designed products: Following the feedback received during the M18 project review

meeting in Brussel, the project demonstrators have been reconsidered by taking the system approach and merging all elements of the circular economy set up that is being developed in ECOBULK. Series of teleconference and face-to-face meetings have been organised collectively and individually for each targeted industrial sector. Each of these meetings had different focus and concerned different aspects of the circular economy model explored in ECOBULK (e.g. business models, end of life, take back systems, digital systems, etc.). The outcome of this work was the development of demonstration maps for all three sectors (furniture, construction and automotive), consisting of several demo activities at each stage of the circular value chain, and a list of partners involved in these demo activities. The maps are supported with the demo cards that summarise the baseline situation and the project value-added innovation enhancing circularity at each stage of the circular value chain. These maps and cards were presented and validated with the consortium during the M24 General Assembly meeting in Coventry (17-18th of June) and can be found in Sections 4.1.3, 4.2.3 and 4.3.3.

The aforementioned demonstration maps were created based on the SITRA's Circular Economy business models for the manufacturing industry (Circular Economy Playbook for Finnish SMEs)¹ and the Consultation on a Guide towards a Circular Built Environment (UKGBC)². Following the SITRA's approach for designing circular value chains (see Figure 2) and circularity principles provided by UKGBC (see Figure 3), the circular value chains for all 3 targeted sectors in ECOBULK were created based on the careful analysis of skills, competences and roles of each consortium partner.

¹ SITRA, 2018. Circular economy business models for the manufacturing industry - Circular Economy Playbook for Finnish SMEs. Available: <https://www.sitra.fi/en/publications/circular-economy-business-models-manufacturing-industry/>

² UKGBC, 2019. Consultation on a Guide towards a Circular Built Environment - supporting clients with practical solutions. Available: <https://www.ukgbc.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/190207-CE-Consultation-Paper.docx>

Business model specific sub-models modify different steps of the value chain to make it circular

Illustrative circular value chain

Most circular opportunities are in the product use phase, bringing companies closer to their customers.

Figure 2: Illustrative circular value chain (Circular Economy Playbook for Finnish SMEs)

Circular principles		Support from Guidance
1. Design out waste		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to ask for it in the project brief/possible metrics • Expected challenges • How you could respond to those expected challenges • Evidence: examples of legal statements, indemnity clauses, etc.
2. Durability and adaptability		
3. Design for dis-assembly		
4. Standardisation		
5. <u>Servitisation</u> and leasing		
6. Low impact new materials		
7. Construction impacts		
8. Reuse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A. asset • B. materials/products on site • C. materials/products for onward reuse • D. materials/products for reuse on new site 		
9. Recycled content/secondary material		

Figure 3: Practically applying circular principles into projects (Consultation on a Guide towards a Circular Built Environment, UKGBC)

In order to create demo maps, the value chains have been divided into specific demo activities presenting ECOBULK solutions as individual sub-models that when taken together and fully implemented, they constitute an extraordinarily powerful combination addressing the challenges preventing circularity at the system level. Different colours on the map represent

different business models and sub-models, as explained in the SITRA’s Circular Economy Playbook for Finnish SMEs (see Figure 4).

Business model	Sub-model	Description	Example synergy: Modular product design enables enhanced reparability and upgradeability
Circular Supply Chain	Build to last	Design products that are durable and easy to repair (e.g. modular).	
	Circular supplies	Use recyclable materials in production, e.g. renewable and bio-based materials, chemicals & energy to increase recovery rates.	
Sharing Platform	Share	Develop solutions that enable increased use of capacity.	
Product as a service	Product as a service	Offer customers to use a product against a subscription fee or usage based charges instead of owning it.	
	Performance as a service	Offer customers to buy a pre-defined service and quality level and commit to guaranteeing a specific result.	
Product Life-extension	Repair & Maintain	Deliver repair and maintenance services to extend the life of existing products in the market.	
	Upgrade	Improve product performance by upgrading existing components with newer ones.	
	Resell	Resell products that have reached their useful life to second and third hand markets.	
	Remanufacture	Take back and perform industry-like restoration or improvement of original functionality of products and remarket them with lower price.	
Recovery & Recycling	Recycle / upcycle	Collect and recover materials of end-of-life products and reuse them in own production.	
	Return	Return wasted parts and materials to the source (e.g. waste and by-products from own production).	

Figure 4: Circular Economy business models (the SITRA’s Circular Economy Playbook for Finnish SMEs)

Updated demo plans: Through discussion meetings and workshops with the end-users and other demo participants, the demo plans presented in M18 have been updated with a more specific breakdown of demo activities, a list of key responsibilities for each demo site, logistics information and specific timelines for demos execution. The updated demo plans are presented in Sections 4.1.4, 4.2.4 and 4.3.4 of this report. It is important to note though that they should not be considered as final and they could be subject to revision during their execution.

4. Definition of demonstration activities

This Section presents the updated demonstration plans compared to the M18 version of the report. For each ECOBULK industrial sector the ‘Business-as-Usual’ scenario is first discussed highlighting the key challenges/barriers that are currently preventing circularity. Updated prototype designs are then presented followed by a comprehensive demo maps for those prototypes enhancing circularity and demonstrating the whole circular value chain set up offered in ECOBULK. Finally, the logistics information presented in M18 have been updated (e.g. demo activities, responsibilities and logistics), and complemented with the timelines for their execution.

4.1. Demonstration products and activities - automotive

4.1.1. Baseline value chain and key challenges preventing circularity

The baseline (linear) value chain for the automotive sector is presented in Figure 5. It is based on ABS as a raw material as this was the baseline

material used for the ECOBULK prototypes. The following information elaborated by Oakdene Hollins can be found with more detail in D8.3.

Figure 5 Linear value chain for automotive

What makes the current value chain linear is as follows:

- **The need for new materials and associated processes to be cost competitive with current materials:** the increasing manufacturing costs and compressing vehicle margins have been problematic for years for the automotive sector, driving the need to save on every component made. The cost-competitiveness of new materials (potentially more circular) is therefore critical and presents a major challenge for their acceptance in the automotive sector.
- **Prolonged product life and end-of-life options:** The End of Life Vehicle Directive has established quantified targets for reuse, recycling and recovery of vehicles and their components. OEMs, importers and distributors must provide systems for the collection of ELVs and where technically feasible, used parts. The challenges of this ELV system in relation to composite components are:
 - Internal composite parts are currently small and difficult to extract. There is currently no market for the recovered composites. These factors make it uneconomic to remove the parts.
 - Composite components have a long life, so are not typically the parts of vehicles that would need replacing.
 - Once dismantling has been undertaken and the larger and higher value parts have been taken from the vehicle, the vehicle is typically shredded and compressed. Composite components therefore form part of the automotive shredder residue (ASR).

- **Technical feasibility of materials recovery:** Assuming plastic and composite components can be retrieved, challenges exist for materials recovery as composites are considered difficult to recycle. Also, the plastics and composites in vehicles use several different polymer families – a problem exacerbated when many different vehicle brands are processed together. In addition to the range of polymer types, recycling of composite components would also be challenging through the embedding of other material types (e.g. metal accessories) or the addition of surface finishing.
- **The existing business models:** A single transaction sale business model is still dominant in the automotive sector. Even if lease business model is considered, the existing practices in the automotive sector fail to support circularity because vehicles are being sold off eventually (either by a third party or authorised dealer) when the lease contract finishes and the track of components/materials is lost preventing the implementation of circular design strategies, such as long use, reuse, maintain and repair, upgrade, refurbish, recycle, etc.

The following sections present the ECOBULK offer and solutions to address some of these challenges preventing circularity in the automotive sector.

4.1.2. *Pilot products*

Prototypes of the internal car parts to be manufactured and demonstrated by MicroCab, FIAT and MAIER as demo sites in WP4 have been designed in WP2 following the design strategy developed by TU Delft.

Material characteristics limits in terms of thermo-mechanical performances have been set and converted to scientific and technical issues as a preparation phase for materials development. CRF, MAIER, MicroCab have been considering mould and components modifications in order to fabricate the final demonstrators. The main focus has been on modularity, mono-/multilayer and fasteners in order to increase product functionality and foster upgrade, reuse, refurbishment, recycling and recovery through clear disassembling and dismantling strategies. Following the material and manufacturing technology selection developed, the design focus on choosing the bio-based materials and fibers (natural and wood), recovered plastics and fibres, binders, fasteners, etc.

MAIER, CRF and MicroCab are optimizing the design of the demonstrators in order to fulfil the needs for disassembly and dismantling and adopt the circular economy approach for the products developed. The list of automotive prototypes that are currently being developed and responsible partners for these prototypes is presented from Figures 6-9.

Figure 6 – Fascia central console (Maier)

Figure 7 – Safety belt bracket (CRF)

Figure 8 – Trim for central panel (CRF)

Figure 9 – Central console cowlings (MicroCab)

4.1.3. Circular value chain and demo activities

A circular value chain and comprehensive demo map for those prototypes enhancing circularity and demonstrating the whole circular set up offered in ECOBULK for the automotive sector are presented in Figures 10-11. The presented map has been divided into specific demo activities across the value chain with different colours representing different sub-models following the SITRA's approach as presented in Figure 4. Once merged together, these individual sub-models constitute a powerful combination addressing the challenges preventing circularity in the automotive sector at the system level.

The green colour clusters all sub-models that relate to circular supply chain activities, such as design of products that are durable and easy to repair (modular), development and supply of recyclable materials to increase recovery rate, as well as manufacturing and final assembly of components and products in line with circular economy principles facilitating easy dismantling and recovery throughout vehicle life cycle. The red colour defines all sub-models and activities that relate to product use, for instance, the implementation of new business models (e.g. product as a service), establishing circular procurement protocols and understanding the customer's preferences and perception of the new circular components and products. The blue colour describes any activities that have to do with a component and product life extension either through implementation of a new business model or interactive digital systems and platforms facilitating product reuse, repair, upgrade, resell and refurbishment. Finally, the orange concerns any end of life activities, whether it is upcycling, recycling, recycling for cascading application, downcycling or energy recovery.

Different circular loops will be demonstrated by different product demonstrators in the automotive sector. For example, CRF and Maier, with the assistance of other value chain partners (e.g. Coventive, Tecnar, Bellver and Aimplas) will be testing and demonstrating the technical and economic feasibility of recovering the EoL bio-based composite materials from automotive components, as well as incorporating materials already coming from the second use cycle (e.g. recovered carbon fibres) into new composite materials. Different EoL routes will be explored for the designed components, including recycling for the same application, recycling for cascading applications (e.g. under the hood parts, carpets, etc,) and downcycling (e.g. for construction application).

New lease business model and product life extension strategies for the automotive sector will be tested with the Microcab's demonstrator. The model assumes taking full responsibility for the product life cycle by OEM. The ownership of the product will remain with Microcab throughout its entire useful life promoting various circular design strategies, such as long use, reuse, maintain and repair, upgrade, refurbish, etc.

More details about each demo activity is summarised in complementary demo cards, which contain the following information: the responsible partners for demo activity, baseline situation preventing circularity, ECOBULK proposition and solutions to enhance circularity, how this proposition will be demonstrated in the project and what is innovative about this proposition. These demo cards are presented along with the circular value chain and demo map in Figures 10-11.

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Figure 10: Automotive circular value

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Figure 11: Demonstration activities in the automotive sector

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
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Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Automotive

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 1 - Circular design framework and tools

Lead Partners involved: OH, TU Delft, Granta, Maier, CRF, Microcab, Exergy

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- TU Delft: development of circular product design strategy framework and tools
- Oakdene Hollins: supporting the development of circular business models
- Granta Design: development of circular material selection methods and tools
- Microcab/ MAIR/CRF: validation of cases, tools and models through case studies
- Exergy: development of business case model for circular economy

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of a comprehensive framework/methodology supporting circularity by design practices in the automotive sector, starting from the circular business model design, moving to the final product design and business case development
- Limited uptake of design for disassembly strategies favouring product life extension.
- Limited consideration of end of life strategy alternatives at early design stages

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- A set of tools/models will be developed in ECOBULK supporting design for circularity
 - Circular design strategy framework for prototype development
 - Material selection tools for smart material choices
 - Fastener toolbox to facilitate assembly and disassembly
 - Business model design tools (i.e. assessment against CE objectives, capability review)
- Identification of main barriers and needs for the uptake of CE strategies in the automotive industry

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Specific case studies for the automotive sector will be focused on the development composites up to automotive industry standards (TuDelft/MAIER/FIAT/Microcab)
 - MAIER/FIAT: Use of high recycled fraction and multi-layer component
 - Microcab: Modular console and composite in the car life cycle
- Granta's material selection tool to be benchmarked against materials already selected (GRANTA)
- Promoting synergies: development of standardization documents (CWAs) based on partners deliverables and including Ecobulk project outputs. (UNE)...

What are the main innovations?

- Circular design framework/methodology consisting of a collection of practical tools/models supporting complex and multidisciplinary design decisions in line with the principles of circular economy
- Material selection toolbox for smart material choices (Granta)

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Sector: Automotive

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 2 – Circular supply

Lead Partners involved: Tecnaro, Coventive Composites, Aimplas, Bellver, CNR

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **Tecnaro:** development of bio-based pellets through compounding
- **Coventive Composites:** development of bio-based and recycled CF pellets through pultrusion
- **Bellver/ Aimplas:** EoL dismantling, final sorting and recovery of light fractions from shredded vehicles
- **CNR:** materials characterisation and testing (including recyclability test)
- **MAIER/FIAT/Microcab:** final end-users

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Composites are becoming very popular materials in the automotive sector because they are light, strong and durable. However, they are also considered difficult to recycle.
- Limited availability of suitable and robust circular material options
- Scarce information on material and components and its use cycles
- Reliability of the sources to ensure homogeneity and enough volume

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Within the scope of Ecobulk more sustainable bio-based composite will be considered:
 - Bio-based matrix and natural fibres (TECNARO)
 - Fiber natural fibres and recycled carbon Fibres (Coventive)
- The possibility to incorporate composite materials coming from recycling (recycled carbon fibres or fibres and plastics recovered from the vehicle EoL) into new components will be studied
- Identification of circular economy opportunities in the current linear value chain through mapping (**Oakdene**).

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Bio-based composites developed by Tecnaro will be assessed by MAIER for prototypes
- Materials formulation with recycled fractions from Coventive will be assessed by MAIER/AIMPLAS
- Development and homogenisation of recycled compounds (AIMPLAS)
- Case study for feasibility study of implementation of sorting technologies at End of Life Vehicles facility (BELLVER)
- Material characterization to meet automotive requirements (CNR/MAIER/FIAT)

What are the main innovations?

- Bio-based composites for the automotive sector (Tecnaro)
- Increased recycled fraction of composites for automotive sector in compliance with industry standards

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Sector: Automotive

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 3 – Product manufacturing/assembly

Lead Partners involved: Tecnar, Coventive Composites, CRF, Maier, Microcab, IRIS

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- Tecnar: supply of pellets by compounding technology
- Coventive Composites: supply of pellets by pultrusion technology
- CRF: injection moulding of semi-structural components
- Maier: injection moulding of multi-layer components
- Microcab: injection moulding of modular dashboard

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of value chain thinking and consideration of circular economy principles when designing in the automotive sector.
- Product aesthetic and mechanical requirements are high and difficult to achieve with bio or recycled materials
- Use of difficult to recycle plastics and mix of plastics in single products

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Automotive components designed and manufactured in line with the circular design framework with the consideration of circular economy strategies and principles (e.g. modularity, easy disassembly, fasteners & connections, etc).
- Components manufactured from renewable and recyclable materials.
- Implementation of circular supply and procurement strategies for component/product production (**Microcab**).

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Development of mould and tooling for prototypes using Ecobulk materials (Maier, CRF and Microcab)
- Manufacture through injection moulding the modular car parts (car fascia, seatbelt bracket, dashboard panel and central console cowlings) using materials developed by **Tecnar and Coventive**. (**MAIER/FIAT/MicroCab**)
- Integration of bio-based composites and high recycled fractions for specific car parts

What are the main innovations?

- Automotive components designed in line with the circular economy principles facilitating easy dismantling and recovery throughout the vehicle life cycle.
- Multi-layer designed components allowing to use more recycled materials (on the back side of the component) with an aesthetic finishes on the front of the component. (**MAIER**)
- Manufacturing of components with bio/recycled materials for relevant components under relevant industrial conditions

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Sector: Automotive

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 4 – Product use (circular business models and procurement)

Lead Partners involved: Microcab, Oakdene Hollins, CRF, Maier, Exergy

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **Microcab:** test and validation of a new business model (product as a service)
- **Oakdene Hollins:** assisting Microcab in business model conceptualisation and assessment
- **CRF:**
- **Maier:**
- **Exergy:** assisting Microcab in business model conceptualisation and assessment

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- A single-transaction sale business model is still dominant in the automotive sector.
- Car are not designed considering difference in the use cycles of parts/components
- Aesthetics and safety are critical issues for end-user that limit the use bio-based and recycled composites

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- A service compensation model, in which the customer pays for continuous access to a product over an agreed period, will be tested by Microcab.
- OEMs will assess and validate the use of parts manufactured using Ecobulk design framework and materials

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Testing and validation of Microcab business model will be supported through simulations and business modelling activities to assess its impact on the composite components (Microcab/OAK/EXE)
- The selected parts to be further validated in the Microcab H2EV model,
- Selected parts to be validated using test beds and standard OEMs procedure (FIAT and MAIER).
- Performance and durability testing of circular designed internal car parts will be done according to the specifications of the OEMs.
- **Maier, CRF and Microcab** will complete upgrade, disassembly and dismantling tests involving end-users at the Demo sites, as well as the activities to perform the user acceptance tests.

What are the main innovations?

- The business model proposed by Microcab is new and disruptive compared to the existing standard practices in the automotive sector.
- The implication of the business models in the composite parts and their design will be addressed

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Sector: Automotive

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 5 – Material recovery/increasing recycling content

Lead Partners involved: Tomra, Aimplas, Bellver, Tecnaro, Coventive, Conenor, NTT

Company name:

Partner's name:

<p>What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomra: end of life sorting and recovery • Bellver: end of life dismantling, sorting and recovery • Aimplas: evaluation of the recycled polymers, ratios and additives for the new compounds based on the recycled pellets • Tecnaro: development of quality pellets coming from recycled materials • Coventive Composites: development of quality pellets coming from recycled materials • Conenor/NTT: testing downcycling opportunities ...
<p>What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most common EoL practices for composites (including bio-based composites) are incineration, landfill and sometimes composting, which are the least desirable options according to the waste hierarchy. - EoL Vehicles are usually shredded – Composites are not recovered and end up in mixed fractions - Separation technologies are not suitable for different plastic fractions
<p>What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECOBULK will test the opportunity, as well as requirements, to close the loop for the composite products in the automotive sector. Coventive and Tecnaro will test the possibility and requirements to reuse materials developed in the project for same applications in n-cycles. - Both will also evaluate the possibility to incorporate materials coming from EoL sorting/recovery activities run by Tomra, Bellver/Aimplas. - As a contingency measure, Conenor and NTT will explore downcycling opportunities for other lower-grade applications.
<p>How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Injection moulded components (CRF, Maier and Microcab) will be subjected to recyclability tests (BELLVER/AIMPLAS/TECNARO). - EoL materials recovered by Tomra, Bellver/Aimplas will be sent to Tecnaro to test their feasibility for the new material production. (AIMPLAS/TECNARO/BELLVER) - Compounded materials and pellets using different recycled fractions will supply to MAIR for manufacturing tests (TECNARO/AIMPLAS/MAIER) - The possibility of recycling automotive composite materials for new lower-grade applications (e.g. nonwovens and construction components) will be tested for outdoor furniture components (Conenor and NTT)
<p>What are the main innovations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECOBULK will test different EoL routes (including cross-sectoral) for recycling automotive composite products and recommend the most optimal solution from the technical, as well as economic and environmental point of view. Recycling is still challenging because, unless it's carbon fibre, the material value is relatively low compared to the cost of recycling it.

4.1.4. Demonstration plans

Specific timelines for the automotive demo activities are presented below (Figures 12-14) considering each demo location (Spain, Italy and UK). Demo sites in Spain (Maier) and Italy (CRF) will be focusing mostly on demonstrating and understanding the implications of circular strategies at the material level, that includes the circular supply and manufacturing, circular procurement and EoL recovery (including the technical, economic and environmental implications of different material recovery routes). The demo site in the UK (Microcab) will be additionally testing different product life extension strategies (e.g. reuse, repair, upgrade and refurbish) by testing and implementing a service compensation (lease) business model.

It is important to note that the proposed timelines in Figures 12-14 may be subject to modification in due course, as well as the logistics information (such as the list of components/ assemblies, quantities, timing, preliminary outline of activities and specific demo responsibilities) provided in complementary tables below the figures.

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GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	3 Fascia central console	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MAIER	05/18 - 05/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	No
		1 assembly tool		Component materials sourcing	MAIER/NetComposites/Te cnaro	05/18 - 03/20		Reassembly	No
	Location	MAIER TECHNOLOGY CENTRE		Prototype manufacture	Maier / MTC	11/19 - 11/20		Repair	No
	Building permit required?	Yes		Prototype responsibility	Maier / MTC	11/19 - 11/20		Recycling/ downcycle	Yes
	Other requirements			Assembly responsibility	Maier / MTC	01/20 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)					
				Disassembly test	Maier / MTC	01/20 - 11/20			
				User acceptance test	Maier / MTC	01/20 - 11/20			

Figure 12: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Spain (Maier)

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FIAT / ITALY

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	20 Safety belt bracket	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	CRF	05/18 - 05/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	No	
		20 Trim for central panel		Component materials sourcing	Coventive/ Tecnaro/ NTT/ Technoplants	05/18 - 07/19		Reassembly	No	
		Floor/trunk carpets		Prototype manufacture	CRF/ NTT/ Technoplants	07/19 - 11/19		Repair	No	
	Location	CRF laboratories?		Prototype responsibility	CRF	11/19 - 11/20		Recycling/ downcycle	Yes	
	Building permit required?	No		Assembly responsibility	CRF	11/19 - 11/20				
	Other requirements			Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)					Energy recovery	No
				Disassembly test	CRF	01/20 - 11/20				
		User acceptance test	CRF	01/20 - 11/20						

Figure 13: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Italy (CRF)

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MICROCAB / UK

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	3- 6 Central console cowlings	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MICROCAB	05/18 - 05/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	Yes
		2 Dashboard highlight panel		Component materials sourcing	Coventive/ Tecnar/ NTT/ Technoplants	05/18 -05/19		Reassembly	Yes
		3-5 Floor/trunk carpets		Prototype manufacture	Third party/ NTT/ Technoplants	05/19 - 09/19		Repair	Yes
	Location	Different venues around Coventry		Prototype responsibility	MICROCAB	09/19 - 11/20		Recycling/ downcycle	Yes
	Building permit required?	Yes		Assembly responsibility	MICROCAB	09/19 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
	Other requirements	Exhibit design		Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	MICROCAB				
				Disassembly test	MICROCAB	09/19 - 03/20			
				User acceptance test	MICROCAB	01/20 - 11/20			

Figure 14: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Microcab)

4.2. Demonstration activities and products - furniture

4.2.1. Baseline value chain and key challenges preventing circularity

The baseline value chain for wood panel-based furniture is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Baseline value chain for wood panel-based furniture products

The challenges to facilitate the circularity of the furniture value chain made from wood are as follows:

- Variations in the amount of waste and recycled wood used in particle board between EU Member States:** There are large variations in the percentage of waste wood used in particle board production across Europe. In particle board production in Italy, 95% of wood comes from recycled materials. In Germany the production of particle board uses 50% of waste wood and in France or Switzerland 5% of waste wood. Key factors in this variability between countries are the availability of virgin wood (Italy for example has very little primary biomass as Italy has very few forests), the availability of supply of recycled wood and the distortion created by the demands of bioenergy. In light of the 2009 Renewable Energy Directive (establishing a target for the EU to fulfil at least 20% of its total energy needs with renewables by 2020), wood has become an important part of renewable energy source (with higher prices paid by the incineration companies than by the particle board manufacturers), which has led to the trend where wood is prematurely incinerated rather than being reused.
- Restrictions on formaldehyde:** Formaldehyde is classified as a carcinogen and is therefore regulated by the EU. It is a naturally occurring organic chemical emitted, for example, from wood. EU standards set two formaldehyde classes – E1, releasing formaldehyde

at less than 0.1 ppm and E2, releasing between 0.1 and 0.3 ppm. In Europe, most of the resins used in particle board are formaldehyde based, but the legislation and customer opinions have driven levels down.

- **Management of end of life and reuse of furniture:** Estimates of furniture waste is generated in Europe each year range from 7.6 million to 10.8 million tonnes. Accounting for 4% of municipal solid waste, 80-90% is incinerated or sent to landfill, with 10% recycled. Reuse levels are low with the rates varying across Europe. Typical routes to reuse are:
 - Formal sales outlets for second-hand goods include charity, antique/junk shops etc as well as online trading platforms such as eBay. In the USA specific online furniture platforms exist, but these have not developed in the EU yet.
 - Informal transfer to family members or friends or donations for social/charitable purposes.
 - A small number of companies take back their own furniture, from large companies (e.g. IKEA) to smaller companies (e.g. Desko and Gispen).
 - Redistribution of furniture through the collection systems of the EPR scheme (e.g. in France).
 - Formal organisations with a recycling and reuse as a mission (e.g. the Furniture Re-use Network in the UK).

- **Particle board recycling:** Particle board is recycled through shredding to make small chips which are then combined with glue to create new wood-based panels. Every time the particle board is shredded, the woodchip becomes smaller resulting in an increase in surface area and therefore more glue is needed. It then becomes harder to meet the formaldehyde regulations. Recycled particle board can currently make up a maximum of 15% of new particle board. Reducing formaldehyde will therefore promote better recyclability through enabling a high percentage of recycled particle board to be used.

- **The use of lower quality and cheaper materials:** Moving away from solid wood to cheaper materials for furniture leads to shorter lifespans for furniture and restricts the potential for second use. It also makes repair and remanufacture less economically viable.

The following sections present the ECOBULK offer and solutions to address some of these challenges preventing circularity in the furniture sector.

4.2.2. Pilot products

Prototypes of the furniture products to be manufactured and demonstrated at demo sites in WP4 have been designed in WP2. The main focus of furniture designing is modularity, mono-/multi-layer and joints/fasteners in order to increase product functionality and foster upgrade, reuse, refurbishment, recycling and recovery through clear disassembling and dismantling strategies.

Following the solutions and products designed in WP2, KEAS will manufacture – and using a more sustainable and low- formaldehyde binder from AkzoNobel - components for Moretti’s product manufacturing in the indoor furniture applications.

The concept developed by Moretti Compact consists of cubic elements that could be used to assemble different furniture solutions (desks, chairs, beds, bookshelf cabinets), which is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Indoor furniture products (Moretti Compact)

The main characteristics of this design are the use of recyclable materials, reusable component, utilization of elements suitable for disassembly and re-assembly (screws, glues), simple lines and shapes, as well as neutral colours.

As a future challenges Moretti Compact is considering introducing glass or aluminium replaceable and recyclable covers, protecting coatings and surfaces, thus ensuring a higher duration of the life cycle.

Regarding ergonomics, a complete screening of reference technical standards for chairs and desks has been conducted. EN 527 -1:20199 (Office furniture – worktable and desks – Part 1: Dimensions) and EN 1335 – 1:2000 (Office furniture – office chair – Dimensions) norms have been complied.

An individuation of a new connecting solution with releasable and invisible elements has also been applied (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Connecting solution with releasable and invisible elements

4.2.3. *Circular value chain and demo activities*

A circular value chain and comprehensive demo map for those prototypes enhancing circularity and demonstrating the whole circular set up offered in ECOBULK for the furniture sector are presented in Figures 18-19. Similarly to the automotive map, the furniture map has been divided into specific

demo activities across the value chain with different colours representing different sub-models as already described in Section 4.1.3 (demo map for the automotive sector).

At the material level, Moretti Compact, KEAS and Akzonobel will be testing the recyclability of new more sustainable particle boards made of virgin and recycled wood chips and low-formaldehyde and formaldehyde-free binders. The use of new binders in the particle boards production should not only reduce the emission of potentially toxic VOCs, it should also improve the recyclability of these boards by enabling inclusion of a high percentage of recycled materials in the n-cycles.

At the product level, Moretti Compact will be testing locally (by engaging the University of Camerino in Italy) the feasibility of implementing a new circular business model by leasing, instead of selling, circularly designed furniture. In a leasing business model, Moretti will maintain a full ownership of the products and will be thus responsible for their delivery, maintenance and take-back when the leasing contract finishes. This will allow Moretti to concrete more on the inner loops of the circular economy model and thus prolong the product life cycle through repair, upgrade and spare part services. In order to develop a cost-effective take-back system, the reverse logistics activities will be optimised with the help of consortium partners from ITENE. Other digital systems, such as QAS and DSS developed by UPC and IRIS, will be also tested by Moretti to make sure that the furniture products have been developed in line with the relevant quality standards and that the most optimal decision is made for the product in the n-cycle once the product returns to Moretti.

The product life extension strategies will be also promoted in other demo locations (in the UK, for example) by providing and testing an online end-user platform for sharing, repairing, reselling, giving away, etc. of second-hand furniture products. As already highlighted in Section 4.2.1, the specific online furniture platforms exist in the USA, but these have not been developed yet in the EU.

More details about each demo activity is summarised in complementary demo cards, which contain the following information: the responsible partners for demo activity, baseline situation preventing circularity, ECOBULK proposition and solutions to enhance circularity, how this proposition will be demonstrated in the project and what is innovative about this proposition. These demo cards are presented along with the circular value chain and demo map in Figures 18-19.

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Figure 18: Furniture circular value chain

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Figure 19: Demonstration activities in the furniture sector

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Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 1 - Circular design framework and tools

Main contributors: OH, Moretti, TU Delft, Granta, Exergy, ITENE

Company name:

Partner's name:

<p>What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TU Delft: development of circular product design strategy framework and tools and supporting Moretti on their prototype development. Oakdene Hollins: development of circular business models frameworks/tools. Kneia: support on business market research/surveys. Granta Design: development of circular material selection tool methods and compiling Ecobulk database. Moretti: pilot case study for framework implementation. Exergy: support on the development of business case. ITENE: labelling design tracking system for traceability purposes.
<p>What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of circular design and non waste mindset due to the lack of information between supply chain and market strategy (eg providing incentives for the consumption of low cost and single use products). Lack of end of life strategy alternatives promotion because of linear consumer model mindset, thus absence of circular business enticement, resulting unfeasible taking back systems and making repair practices uneconomic.
<p>What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and validation of a set of tools/models supporting design for circularity, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular design strategy framework for prototype development Material selection tools for smart material choices Fastener toolbox to facility assembly and disassembly Business model design tools (i.e. assessment against CE objectives, capability review) Design a labelling system to trace the entire product lifecycle. Promotion of circular design life-long products (design trend).
<p>How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of structured business model methodology for the assessment of Moretti's case study. Review of Moretti capabilities and opportunities review (Oakdene/Moretti). Material selection tool to be benchmarked against material already selected. Case study for particle board and binder selection (Granta/KEAS/Akzonobel). Fastener toolbox developed by TuDelft to be used by Moretti in prototypes (TuDelft/Moretti). Support Moretti in selecting tracking system for furniture products (Moretti/ITENE). Promoting synergies: development of standardization documents (CWAs) based on partners deliverables and including Ecobulk project outputs. (UNE) Scientific publications/white paper on Circular Product Design (TuDelft/Oakdene).
<p>What are the main innovations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular design framework with a practical application for SME (OH/TuDelft/Exergy/KNEIA) Fastener tool box: large database including circular indicators for the selection (TuDelft) Integrating labelling and traceability considerations at early stages of the product design (ITENE) Material selection toolbox for smart material choices (Granta)

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Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 2 – Circular supply

Main contributors: Cranfield University, Akzo, KEAS, FCBA, CNR

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- Cranfield University: development of bio-based binders.
- Akzonobel: development of bio/green binder: low formaldehyde/ formaldehyde free.
- KEAS: particle board material formulation
- FCBA: expertise and recycled material samples
- CNR: material/product characterization and testing
- Technoplants/NTT: production of soft non-wovens

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of information for more circular/green material procurement
- Lack of material use cycles information and reliability of the sources, making sorting process infeasible.
- Homogeneity of general waste streams and scarcity of information of material and components

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Developing new/greener material formulations:
 - Bio binders (**Akzonobel/Cranfield**)
 - Particle boards with higher recycled fractions of particle board (**Akzonobel/KEAS**).
- Identification of circular economy opportunities in the current linear value chain through mapping (**Oakdene**).
- Development of non-wovens by airlaid technology without the use of chemical binders (**NTT/Technoplants**)
- Material QAS to secure the quality required for the final product (**UPC**)
- Assessing of two material conditioning technologies: plasma and DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- New green low formaldehyde binder formulations developed at lab and pilot scale benchmarked against current materials (**Cranfield/Akzonobel**)
- Lab scale validation of bio/green binder and low/free formaldehyde particle boards (**Cranfield/Akzonobel/KEAS**).
- Testing panels recyclability through lab tests (**Cranfield/Akzo/Keas/NTT/Technoplants**)
- Production of panels made by non-wovens compression (**NTT/Technoplants**)

What are the main innovations?

- Green/bio low/free formaldehyde binder formulations
- Increased recycled particle board fraction
- Conditioning technologies progressing on the TRL: plasma/ DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)
- Valorisation of low value of fibre waste streams (**NTT**)

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 3 – Product manufacturing/assembly

Main contributors: KEAS, Moretti, IRIS, CNR, NTT and Technoplants

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- KEAS: manufacturing of particle boards
- Moretti: final product manufacturing and assembly.
- IRIS: development of a Quality Assurance System (QAS)
- CNR: material/product characterization and testing
- NTT/Technoplants: production of soft non-wovens

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Product design without circular thinking (i.e. design for disassembly, modularity, etc).
- Linear fashion consumption trends, disposable products and global low cost manufacturing
- Lack of end of life strategy alternatives promotion because of linear consumer model mindset, absence of circular business enticement and no promotion of circular manufacturing practices (e.g. resourcing, fasteners circularity).

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Developing low/free formaldehyde particle boards with high recycled fractions (**Akzonobel/KEAS/Cranfield**).
- Ensure the use of current manufacture lines for Ecobulk products, thus facilitating replicability at SME scale (**KEAS/Moretti**).
- Providing tools for assessing and improving the efficiency in the manufacturing line through QAS (**IRIS**).
- Implementation of circular supply and procurement strategies for component/product production (**Moretti**).

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Manufacturing of pilot batches of particle boards with Ecobulk materials (**Cranfield/Akzonobel/KEAS** * to be carried out at Fraunhofer).
- Development of a set of modular furniture components and integration of simple fastener solutions (bed, table, shelf, chair) – Cube concept (**Moretti**)
- Development of a set of modular furniture components using non-wovens and particle boards (**FCBA/NTT/Technoplants**)
- Validation of QAS using Moretti's case study (**IRIS**)
- Implementing labelling design tracking system in Ecobulk furniture (**ITENE**).

What are the main innovations?

- Integration of new and formaldehyde low/free binders in an actual furniture manufacturing line (**KEAS/Akzonobel/Moretti**)
- Modular cubic-element furniture with simple fastener solutions (**Moretti**)
- Market products with new/greener formulation: Compressed non-wovens for bookcase and chairs; and soft panels for sofa (**NTT/Technoplants**).

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 4 – Product use (circular business models and procurement)

Main contributors: Moretti (Italian University), Coventry/Warwick/Cranfield/ Italian University, Oakdene Hollins

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- Moretti: product manufacturer.
- Coventry Uni, Warwick Uni and Italian universities: physical demo sites (student accommodation and university meeting rooms) and performance of user acceptance test.
- Warwick and Cranfield University: End user information and university procurement assessment.
- Oakdene Hollins: supporting implementation of Moretti's business case.
- Lipor offices: potential physical demo sites and end user tests?

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Linear mindset of end users (e.g. university, facility manager or final users) in end of life strategies and lack of awareness on circular products.
- Lack of understanding of potential gains from circular products: Cost benefits
- Lack of incentives for end users to take up innovative products
- Limited offer on circular design furniture products due to companies selling commodities products

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Identifying barriers for business models implementation through Moretti's case study and universities current procurement.
- Understanding user needs through end user acceptance tests in several environments (e.g. meeting room, student accommodation, outdoor furniture).
- Set up end user platform to trace the sustainable value of the furniture along its value chain based on circular principles.
- Raising user awareness about circular products.

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Deployment of two indoor meeting rooms Ecobulk furniture (**Warwick University and Lipor facilities**),
- Furnishing 12 student accommodation rooms in Coventry University (**Coventry University**)
- Furnishing X student accommodation rooms in Italian University (Camerino University) (**Moretti**)
- Pilot of take back system business model in Italy (**Moretti, Oakdene**)
- Demo exercises: assembly/disassembly test and user acceptance test at the different demo sites (**Coventry Uni, Warwick Uni, Lipor and Moretti**).
- Review an outline of circular procurement procedure recommendations (**Warwick University, Coventry University and Lipor**).

What are the main innovations?

- Circular economy business model for a medium enterprise.
- Circular procurements recommendations (Universities).
- Methodology for end user acceptance test for circular principles adoption (**Coventry University, FCBA**)

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 5 –Product life extension/ECOBULK digital systems

Main contributors: UPC, ITENE, Moretti, Exergy, Warwick University, Coventry University

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- UPC: decision support system
- ITENE: logistic platform and tracking system.
- Moretti: test and validation of a new business model (product as a service)
- Exergy: end user platform
- Warwick Uni, Coventry Uni and Camerino Uni: pilot for end user platform

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of stakeholder engagement and community consciousness.
- Limited data for traceability – material/product location/condition
- Limited promotion of product life extension alternatives (share, repair & maintain, upgrade,...)
- Non clear (reverse) logistics strategies

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Building local networks. Identification of key stakeholders and promote their activity within the circular supply approach. UK and Italy as a case study scenario.
- Engaging local authorities to identify barriers for circular economy implementation
- Providing ICT tools for stakeholders and final end users
- Provide the information for implementation of traceability technologies

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Engaging a network of local stakeholder
- Piloting stakeholder and end user platform in UK and Italy (**Warwick University, Coventry University, Camerino University**)
 - Decision support system (**UPC, Exergy**).
 - Logistics platform/traceability technologies (**ITENE**).
 - Quality Assurance System (**IRIS**)
 - Engaging university/local communities in circular economy activities through end user ICT tool (**UPC, Exergy**)

What are the main innovations?

- ICT tool for engagement (**UPC, EXERGY**)
- Decision support system fostering circular economy options (**UPC**)

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Furniture

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 6 – Material recovery/increasing recycling content

Main contributors: KEAS, AKZONOBEL, TOMRA, FCBA, NTT

Company name:

Partner's name:

<p>What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KEAS: evaluating feasibility of larger recycled fractions integration. • Akzonobel: assessing compatibility of green binders in new formulations • TOMRA: material sorting expertise. • FCBA: expertise in material recovery/ recycle material sampling • NTT: recovery of fibres/textiles • UPC : DSS (UPC)
<p>What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heterogenous recovered material streams and lack of sorting strategies - Missing product design which is considering recyclability / reusability (TOMRA) - Lack of refurbishing options/maintenance mindset together with inherent low value of the products, resulting second life furniture no attractive within the linear economic market (ISWA)
<p>What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating through the design more uniform recovered material streams (design for disassembly) - Develop sorting programs for certain material streams (TOMRA) - Fostering the use of large recycled fractions through material formulation (KEAS) - Promoting the uptake of large recycled material fractions through research on circular business models - Development of a decision support system to assess action according to sustainability criteria (UPC). - Reverse logistics through end user platforms (UK and Italian universities). (KEAS) - Reporting of barriers and opportunities to enhance circularity within material recovery
<p>How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Testing recyclability of new and recycled components using Ecobulk demonstrators in UK and Italy (KEAS,CNR). - Promoting local circular networks for the product recovery at end of life through furniture case study in UK and Italy. - Establishing collaboration with other sectors for material sourcing and valorisation (already existing initiatives in France/Eco Mobilier/Valdelia and Italy/Rilegno).(Exergy) - Testing conditioning technologies to facilitate integration of recovered materials in new material formulations (DMSO and plasma). (NTT/IRIS)
<p>What are the main innovations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More homogeneous material sources through out the cycles. (TOMRA) - Adapted sorting technologies for SME business models scale (TOMRA) - Disseminating product design importance to achieve circular product chain models.

4.2.4. *Demonstration plans*

Specific timelines for the furniture demo activities are presented below (Figures 20-23) considering each demo location (Italy, Portugal and the UK).

The implementation of a leasing business model in Italy (Moretti) will allow to test different product life extension strategies (such as reuse, upgrade repair, etc.). The life extension strategies will be also supported in other demo sites in the UK through development of an online end-user platform enabling to share, reuse, resell or give away of second-hand furniture. All demo sites in the furniture sector will be involved in the development of circular procurement protocols and in conducting the user-acceptance study. The recyclability and EoL strategies for the designed furniture will be tested primarily by Moretti, KEAS and Akzonobel, although other demo owners will be also looking for opportunities to engage local particle boards manufacturers to test the recyclability of newly developed materials and close the loop at the local level.

It is important to note that the proposed timelines in Figures 20-23 may be subject to modification in due course, as well as the logistics information (such as the list of components/ assemblies, quantities, timing, preliminary outline of activities and specific demo responsibilities) provided in complementary tables below the figures.

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

MORETTI / ITALY

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	12 student rooms	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	until 07/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	Yes
		1 meeting room		Component materials sourcing	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	Continuous		Reassembly	Yes
	Location	Camerino University Campus & Moretti showroom		Prototype manufacture	KEAS/ AKZONOBEL	05/19 - 09/19		Repair	Yes
	Demo site timeframe	12/19-11/20		Shipping responsibility	MORETTI	Dec-19		Recycling/ downcycle	Yes
	Building permit required?	Yes/No		Prototype responsibility	MORETTI	12/19 - 11/20			
	Other requirements			Assembly responsibility	MORETTI	Dec-19		Energy recovery	No
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	MORETTI	Dec-19			
				Disassembly test	MORETTI	several times			
				User acceptance test	MORETTI	12/19, 01/20 and 05/20			

Figure 20: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Italy (Moretti)

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LIPOR / PORTUGAL

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 meeting room	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	until 07/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	No
	Location	Lipor facilities		Component materials sourcing	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	Continuous		Reassembly	No
	Demo site timeframe	12/19-12/20		Prototype manufacture	KEAS/ AKZONOBEL	05/19 - 09/19		Repair	No
	Building permit required?	YES/NO		Shipping responsibility	MORETTI	Dec-19		Recycling/ downcycle	No
	Other requirements			Prototype responsibility	LIPOR	12/19 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
				Assembly responsibility	LIPOR	Dec-19			
Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)			LIPOR	Dec-19					
		Disassembly test	LIPOR	several times					
		User acceptance test	LIPOR	Continuous					

Figure 21: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Portugal (Lipor)

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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COVENTRY / UK

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	12 student rooms	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	until 07/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	end user platform
		1 meeting room		Component materials sourcing	MORETTI/KEAS/AKZONOBEL	Continuous		Reassembly	within university
	Location	Future Lets & Coventry University Campus		Prototype manufacture	KEAS/ AKZONOBEL	05/19 - 09/19		Repair	stakeholder platform
	Demo site timeframe	09/19-09/20		Shipping responsibility	MORETTI	Dec-19		Recycling/ downcycle	No
	Building permit required?	Yes		Prototype responsibility	COVENTRY	12/19 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
	Other requirements			Assembly responsibility	COVENTRY	Dec-19			
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	COVENTRY	Dec-19			
Disassembly test			COVENTRY	several times					
		User acceptance test	COVENTRY	12/19, 01/20 and 05/20					

Figure 22: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Coventry University)

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WARWICK / UK INDOOR FURNITURE

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 meeting room	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	MORETTI/KEAS /AKZONOBEL	until 07/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	through end user platform
	Location	Warwick University Campus		Component materials sourcing	MORETTI/KEAS /AKZONOBEL	Continuous		Reassembly	within University
	Demo site timeframe	12/19-12/20		Prototype manufacture	KEAS/ AKZONOBEL	05/19 - 09/19		Repair	stakeholder platforms
	Building permit required?	Yes/No		Shipping responsibility	MORETTI	Dec-19		Recycling/ downcycle	No
	Other requirements			Prototype responsibility	WARWICK	12/19 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
				Assembly responsibility	WARWICK	Dec-19			
		Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	WARWICK	Dec-19					
		Disassembly test	WARWICK	several times					
		User acceptance test	WARWICK	Continuous					

Figure 23: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Warwick University)

4.3. Demonstration activities and products - construction

4.3.1. Baseline value chain and key challenges preventing circularity

As presented in D8.3, there are two potential value chain baselines that could be used for the construction demonstration.

- Baseline 1:** The products themselves could be used to substitute similar products made from a wide possible range of materials (e.g. wood, steel, aluminium, felt and tile roofs etc), as well as composites made from different materials (including current Conenor composites using recycled materials).
- Baseline 2:** An alternative route for waste thermoset composites. At end of life, options for thermoset composites are limited (currently primarily storage, landfill or incineration). A small amount of waste thermoset is used in cement kilns (EoL solution) and research is being undertaken to extract valuable fibres through pyrolysis (energy intensive) and chemical processes (resulting complex chemicals), but these approaches are not yet commercially viable except for examples of a small amount of carbon fibres. Work is also ongoing as to how larger thermoset composite structures can be reused with cascading options of downsizing and reuse. Including shredded glass fibre containing thermosets as reinforcement in thermoplastic composites adds to the potential of finding further uses for complex thermoset waste streams.

Baseline 2 allows for the consideration of greater links between thermoset and thermoplastic value chains and potential new business models and it is presented in Figure 24.

Figure 24 Baseline value chain for composites in construction

The challenges to facilitate the circularity of the composites in construction are as follows:

- Virgin materials are primarily petrochemical-based polymers and glass fibres, but demand for alternatives is growing:** Many of the larger companies make note of the use of natural fibres and

bio-resins on their websites. There are also specialist providers of bio-based composites. Indications are that the market is growing³. Research into bio-based resins and natural fibres has been around for many years, but possibly the fluctuating (often relatively cheap) price of oil and a historic lack of customer demand or willingness to pay more for bio-based composites has contributed to the relatively slow uptake of these products. Certain extruded composite products known as WPCs have included recycled plastics for some time - decking, benches and (more recently) window frames are common examples. Waste wood is also used as a fibre in some outdoor furniture applications. Supply chains for these secondary raw materials are well established through plastic recovery and recycling providers.

- **The distribution network does not facilitate take back of products:** There are many different relationships between product producers and users within composite products and construction. Some will be bespoke, and therefore the relationship will be direct between designer, buyer and composite manufacturer. For commoditized products, distribution can be through a network of one or more distributors, including through specialist construction outlets, domestic home improvement outlets or product specific retailers direct to business or domestic buyers. There is therefore no link between value chain members (composite materials suppliers and manufacturers) and the product owners. There is currently no economically beneficial reason for distributors to play a role in recovering products.
- **Producers are not accountable for the products they put on the market:** At the end of product life, producers of composite materials for the construction sector currently have no obligations or responsibility for the products put onto the market (outside of guarantee obligations).
- **There are no recognized routes for composite product recovery within construction:** Composite products currently have no recognized recovery route, and the current lack of information about materials in the product make this even more difficult. Broader trends in sustainability and construction, such as a shift from demolition to deconstruction and materials passports, could support greater recovery at end of life if appropriate product recovery routes were established. The lack of current commercial processes and applications for end of life composite products does not supply any commercial drivers to support recovery.

³ [Global biobased resins market growth](#), Business wire, May 2018

- **Price plays a crucial role in bulk construction products:** Construction products are manufactured typically in bulk volumes in large scale industrial processes to bring cost of manufacture down to minimum. Margins are tight as well as competition and moreover in most applications national building codes stipulate what materials are allowed to be used in each case. Composite products make no difference in this sense but in case they may offer new valuable properties, they are of interest and possibly acceptable at a small premium price.

4.3.2. *Pilot products*

Prototypes of the new building products to be manufactured and demonstrated at demo sites in WP4 structural applications have been designed following the design strategy developed in WP2 and the material/manufacturing selection chosen in the consortium and the framework set.

The prototypes have been designed depending on (1) purpose: public buildings or residential buildings; (2) functionality: room separation, lounging, insulation (thermal and/or noise), etc.; (3) form and construction: single layer, multilayer, sandwich, etc.; and, (4) health & safety. The main focus is on modularity, as well as multilayer, edge bands and joints/connections solutions in order to increase product functionality and foster upgrade, reuse, refurbishment, recycling and recovery through clear disassembling and dismantling strategies.

Among the large number of potential circular designed components, the ECOBULK concept is being validated using three (3) key type of single and multilayer weather resistant composite components (planks/boards, panels and profiles) using the CONEX[®]-extrusion technology and chosen agglomerated composite material formulations optimised in WP3 by Conenor.

The responsibility of extruded composite component supplies for the outdoor furniture and construction demonstrations and ECOBULK demo sites/partners lies with Conenor; however, the design activities are being performed by other project partners (e.g. demo owners or associated parties).

Applications include benches and tables for parks and other public places for visitors to rest and for recreation. The preliminary conceptual sketches developed for KymiRing in Finland and Lipor in Portugal by their chosen architects (Sankari and Inbicta) are presented in Figures 25-30. Type of outdoor furniture to be demonstrated in France by a local municipal contact is under study by FCBA. Exergy is responsible for UK prototype's design and their related demo activities, where several outdoor shelters will be

demonstrated in Warwick University, Coventry University and Cranfield University.

New and more ambitious pilot products have been added to the demonstration plans for the construction sector compared with the project proposal stage. For example, simple decking and fencing systems, previously considered in the project, have been replaced with more complex, but still considered as light and possible to deploy construction structures, such as bike shelter, information cabins, and shelters, etc. The inclusion of these new designs allows to test and demonstrate more circular economy and material strategies (such as easy assembly/disassembly, modularity, multifunction, new connection and fastener selection, etc. and **in particular structural construction designs** from new recycled composite products with fibre reinforcements available from waste and till today non-recyclable FRP-materials such as EoL wind turbine blades). Same as with the furniture sector, new product construction designs and developments have also brought attention of new and more promising demo sites where these products could be deployed and tested. Apart from Warwick University and Coventry University, FCBA has engaged two local outdoor furniture manufacturers to test the applicability of ECOBULK components in outdoor tables and benches.

A list of construction product designs and responsible partners is as follow:

Figure 25: Outdoor bench concept (KymiRing, Finland)

1844_A-1.001

KYMIRING/ECOBULK

SHELTER MODULE
CONCEPT SKETCH
1 : 50
27.9.2018

ARKKITEHDIT
SANKARI
Raatimiehenkatu 6F, 00140 HELSINKI
Tuomas Klaus, arkkitehti
+358-503033396
info@sankari.fi

Figure 26: Shelter module for people (Kymiring, Finland)

1844_A-1.003

KYMIRING/ECOBULK

INFO CABIN
CONCEPT SKETCH
1 : 50
27.9.2018

ARKKITEHDIT
SANKARI
Raatimiehenkatu 6F, 00140 HELSINKI
Tuomas Klaus, arkkitehti
+358-503033396
info@sankari.fi

Figure 27: Info cabin (KymiRing, Finland)

Figure 28: Tree bench (Lipor Adventure Park, Portugal)

Figure 29: Drinking Fountain (Lipor Adventure Park, Portugal)

Figure 30: Waste collection point (Lipor Adventure Park, Portugal)

Figure 31: Outdoor benches and tables (FCBA/Grossfillex & Sineugraff, France)

Figure 32: Multi-purpose convertible shelter (Exergy/Coventry University, UK)

Figure 33: Multi-purpose convertible shelter (Exergy/Coventry University, UK)

Meeting on top of the hill

Floor plans

Option 1: No decking

Option 2: Part decking

Option 3: Full decking area

Figure 34: Multi-purpose convertible shelter (Exergy/Warwick University/Cranfield University)

4.3.3. Circular value chain and demo activities

A circular value chain and comprehensive demo map for those prototypes enhancing circularity and demonstrating the whole circular set up offered in ECOBULK for the construction sector are presented in Figures 35-36. Similarly to the automotive and furniture maps, the construction map has been divided into specific demo activities across the value chain with different colours representing different sub-models as already described in Section 4.1.3 (demo map for the automotive sector).

The Conenor's product lifecycle is fed by the materials outflow of thermoset GFRP products, for example wind turbine blades, boats & yachts etc. The main recovery strategy is mechanical recycling and re-manufacturing in the Conenor's or comparable extrusion processes, which will be demonstrated as part of the EoL strategy for the construction sector. The extruded planks and panels are made substantially of waste materials and can be recycled into new planks and panels. The composite extrusion tests will be conducted by Conenor as the technology owner and verified by Aimplas by shredding and extruding in the conventional type extruders that are available in the market. Aimplas will also test the feasibility of pelletizing and compounding into granules of GFRP-waste containing Conenor agglomerated formulations for extrusions, injection and compression moulding thermoplastic processes. Labelling, tracking and material passport will be developed and tested for the GFRP boards to ensure their collection after an extra-long lifetime and further reuse in the next cycles. The aim of these tests is to prove the replicability of Conenor's solutions developed in Ecobulk by third parties and thus strengthening the obtained results and opening the new routes for their exploitation.

Considering that Conenor is a R&D SME acting as OEM for the sake of the project, different circular business model opportunities will be explored, with the primary being to offer the proprietary plastics conversion technology both for producing new raw materials as well as extruded composites on a license basis. Other demo owners will be looking for opportunities to engage local extrusion companies potentially interested in Conenor's technology to test the recyclability of newly developed materials in the conventional type extruders that are available in the market and to be able to close the loop at the local level. Return logistics should be also quite local (due to value of material), while the products could be sold worldwide. Furthermore, Conenor has made a close contact with one of the world largest wind turbine blade manufacturer who is highly interested to monitor as a stakeholder the ECOBULK-project outcome and understand how to engage itself in recycling their blades.

Additionally, parts will be harvested and reused from deconstructed buildings, which were designed for easy disassembly, replacement, repair and recovery. The digital tools and platforms developed in the project (e.g. DSS and end-user platform) will also support the share, reuse, repair and

resell strategies by building local networks and engaging local stakeholders and end users.

More details about each demo activity is summarised in complementary demo cards, which contain the following information: the responsible partners for demo activity, baseline situation preventing circularity, ECOBULK proposition and solutions to enhance circularity, how this proposition will be demonstrated in the project and what is innovative about this proposition. These demo cards are presented along with the circular value chain and demo map in Figures 35-36.

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Figure 35: Construction circular value chain

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Figure 36: Demonstration activities for the construction sector

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 1 - Circular design framework and tools

Lead partners involved : OH, Conenor, TU Delft, Granta, Exergy

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- Conenor: Expertise and know-how on extrusion and agglomeration technologies and circular waste materials
- Oakdene Hollins: development of circular business models frameworks/tools.
- Kneia: support on business market research/surveys.
- Granta Design: development of circular material selection tool methods and compiling Ecobulk database.
- Exergy: support on the development of business case and
- ITENE: labelling design tracking system for traceability purposes.
- **Demo site responsible** (Conenor, LIPOR, FCBA, Exergy): implementation of circular design framework in the demo sites.

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of circular design and non waste mindset due to the lack of information within supply chain and market strategy (eg providing incentives for the consumption of low cost and single use products).
- Limited uptake of design for disassembly strategies favouring product life extension.
- Lack of end of life strategy alternatives to deal with thermoplastics and complex wood waste streams

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Design and validation of a set of tools/models supporting design for circularity, such as:
 - Circular design strategy framework for prototype development
 - Material selection tools for smart material choices
 - Fastener toolbox to facility assembly and disassembly
 - Business model design tools (i.e. assessment against CE objectives, capability review)
- Development of technologies to use thermoset FRP-waste for the conversion into new sellable goods.
- Design a labelling system to trace the entire product lifecycle.
- Promotion of circular design life-long products (design trend).

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Validation of structured business model methodology for the assessment of FRP-based pellets case study (Oakdene/Conenor).
- Material selection tool to be benchmarked against material already selected. Case study for recycled FRP material (Granta/Conenor).
- Fastener toolbox developed by TuDelft to be used by construction demo site responsibles in the design of theprotoypes (TuDelft/Conenor/Lipor/FCBA/Exergy).
- Defining and implementing a technology (e.g. QR codes, RFID) for product tracking at the demo sites(Moretti/ITENE).
- Promoting synergies: development of standardization documents (CWAs) based on partners deliverables and including Ecobulk project outputs. (UNE)
- Scientific publications/white paper on Circular Product Design (TuDelft/Oakdene).

What are the main innovations?

- Circular design framework with a practical application for SME (OH/TuDelft/Exergy/KNEIA)
- Fastener tool box: large database including circular indicators for the selection (TuDelft)
- Integrating labelling and traceability considerations at early stages of the product design (ITENE)
- Material selection toolbox for smart material choices (Granta)
- Innovative approach to valorise FRP waste through multi-layer product design (Conenor).

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Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 2 – Circular supply

Lead partners involved : Conenor, FCBA, Aimplas, Technoplants, CNR Link stakeholders: VIROL, Valdelia,

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **Conenor:** agglomeration technology, choice of alternative feedstock materials from waste for agglomeration processing
- **FCBA:** expertise and recycle material samples
- **Aimplas:** verification of pellet and granule manufacturing from Conenor made agglomerates
- **Technoplants:** Airlaid technology to produce non-wovens to be compressed – (**NTT**)
- **CNR:** material/product characterization and testing
- **Link stakeholders (Virol, Valdelia):** material sourcing

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of material use cycles information and reliability of the sources, making sorting process infeasible.
- Homogeneity of general waste streams and scarcity of information of material and components
- Limited options for valorising thermoset waste streams

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Identification of circular economy opportunities in the current linear value chain at material and component level (**Conenor/OH**)
- Know-how on agglomeration and mix formulation and pelletizing and compounding for component injection molding, compression molding and other plastic processing (**Conenor**).
- Development of non-wovens by airlaid technology without the use of chemical binders (**NTT/Technoplants**)
- Assessing of two material conditioning technologies: plasma and DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Development of robust and consistent material formulations for agglomeration using recycled-FRP streams– (**Conenor**)
- Verification of the suitability of agglomerated material formulations for manufacturing compacted pellets and compounded granules (**Aimplas**)
- Integration and valorisation of mixed material fractions from different sources – (**Conenor, FCBA, Virol, etc.**)
- Recyclability tests to validate material performance throughout the cycles – (**Conenor**) and validation and recyclability tests for non-wovens (**NTT**)

What are the main innovations?

- Material formulation methodology and manufacturing by agglomeration – (**Conenor**)
- Integration of optimized high-fractions of recycled FRC – (**Conenor**)
- Valorisation and integration of recycled FRC fractions in volume applications/ cross-sectorial synergies (**Conenor**)
- Conditioning technologies progressing on the TRL: plasma/ DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)

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GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 2 – Circular supply

Lead partners involved : Conenor, FCBA, Aimplas, Technoplants, CNR Link stakeholders: VIROL, Valdelia

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **Conenor:** agglomeration technology, choice of alternative feedstock materials from waste for agglomeration processing
- **FCBA:** expertise and recycle material samples
- **Aimplas:** verification of pellet and granule manufacturing from Conenor made agglomerates
- **Technoplants:** Airlaid technology to produce non-wovens to be compressed – (NTT)
- **CNR:** material/product characterization and testing
- **Link stakeholders (Virol, Valdelia):** material sourcing

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of material use cycles information and reliability of the sources, making sorting process infeasible.
- Homogeneity of general waste streams and scarcity of information of material and components
- Limited options for valorising thermoset waste streams

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Identification of circular economy opportunities in the current linear value chain at material and component level (**Conenor/OH**)
- Know-how on agglomeration and mix formulation and pelletizing and compounding for component injection molding, compression molding and other plastic processing (**Conenor**).
- Development of non-wovens by airlaid technology without the use of chemical binders (**NTT/Technoplants**)
- Assessing of two material conditioning technologies: plasma and DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Develop of robust and consistent material formulations for agglomeration using recycled-FRP streams– (**Conenor**)
- Verification of the suitability of agglomerated material formulations for manufacturing compacted pellets and compounded granules (**Aimplas**)
- Integration and valorisation of mixed material fractions from different sources – (**Conenor, FCBA, Virol, etc.**)
- Recyclability tests to validate material performance throughout the cycles – (**Conenor**) and validation and recyclability tests for non-wovens (**NTT**)

What are the main innovations?

- Material formulation methodology and manufacturing by agglomeration – (**Conenor**)
- Integration of optimized high-fractions of recycled FRC – (**Conenor**)
- Valorisation and integration of recycled FRC fractions in volume applications/ cross-sectorial synergies (**Conenor**)
- Conditioning technologies progressing on the TRL: plasma/ DMSO (**IRIS/NTT**)
- Multilayer products with CONEX®-extruder utilizing FRP-waste in different material formulations (**Conenor**)

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Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 4 – Product use (circular business models and procurement)

Lead partners involved : Conenor, Lipor, Warwick University and Coventry University, Cranfield University, FCBA, Exergy

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **Conenor:** Material/product supplier for prototypes at demosites. Demo site coordinator and Kymiring demo site responsible (FI)
- **Lipor:** Lipor demo site responsible (PT)
- **Warwick, Coventry and Cranfield University:** Campus demo site responsible (UK)
- **FCBA:** FCBA demo site responsible (FR)
- **Exergy:** demo coordinator and validation support

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Linear mindset of end users (e.g. university, facility manager or final users) in end of life strategies and lack of awareness on circular products
- Linear mindset in use of products assets and new circular business models implementation for medium and small companies.
- Current wooden in outdoor moist conditions like sawn timber absorb water causing loss of properties and bacteria growth. Therefore, products have of short life cycle and the circular value at the end of life is marginal .
- Limited offer on circular design furniture products due to companies selling commodities products.
- Lack of incentives for end users to take up innovative products.

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Designing new circular products utilizing waste material fractions and aimed for structural construction applications.
- Designing new circular product assemblies matching with properties developed in the new products .
- Identifying requirements and barriers for deployment and use of light structures integrating large recycled FRP fractions.
- Understanding user needs and perception through end user acceptance tests in several demosites.

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Deployment and installation of modular structures based on Ecobulk single/multilayer components at the demosites.
 - Demonstrators/deployment: at Kymiring (FI), Warwick University (UK), Coventry University (UK), LIPOR (PT), FCBA (FR), Cranfield University (?) – Shelters, outdoor furniture, cabins,...
- Demo exercise: Itinerant structures with the aim to test disassembly practices and material maintenance and also through user acceptance test – (**Coventry University, Warwick University, FCBA**).

What are the main innovations?

- Prove circular extruded composites made up to 90-w. from recycled materials and including FRP-waste are suitable to use in several structural volume applications in constructions.
- Prove A) new recycled and circular materials in pellet and granule form and B) extruded composites made thereof up...

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Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 5 –Product life extension/ECOBULK digital systems

Lead partners involved : UPC, ITENE, Conenor, Warwick University, Coventry University, Exergy

Company name:

Partner's name:

What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?

- **UPC:** decision support system
- **ITENE:** logistic platform and tracking system.
- **Moretti:** test and validation of a new business model (product as a service)
- **Exergy:** end user platform
- **Warwick Uni, Coventry Uni and Italian Uni:** pilot for end user platform

What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?

- Lack of stakeholder engagement and community consciousness.
- Limited data for traceability – material/product location/condition
- Limited promotion of product life extension alternatives (share, repair & maintain, upgrade,...)
- Non clear (reverse) logistics strategies

What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?

- Building local networks. Identification of key stakeholders and promote their activity within the circular supply approach. UK and Italy as a case study scenario.
- Engaging local authorities to identify barriers for circular economy implementation
- Providing ICT tools for stakeholders and final end users
- Provide the information for implementation of traceability technologies

How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?

- Engaging a network of local stakeholder
- Piloting stakeholder and end user platform in UK and Italy (**Warwick University, Coventry University**)
 - Decision support system (**UPC, Exergy**).
 - Logistics platform/traceability technologies (**ITENE**).
 - Engaging university/local communities in circular economy activities through end user ICT tool (**UPC, Exergy**)
- Testing product circularity of Conenor on different climate areas in cold areas (KymiRing-FI) and warm areas (Lipor-PT) and checking their structural characteristics afterwards (disassembled components will be back to Conenor for re-manufacturing through shredding and direct extrusion).

What are the main innovations?

- ICT tool for engagement (**UPC, EXERGY**)
- Decision support system fostering circular economy options (**UPC**)

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Sector: Construction

Demonstration activity: Demo activity 6 – Material recovery/increasing recycling content

Lead partners involved: Conenor, TOMRA, FCBA

Company name:

Partner's name:

<p>What is the role of each partner in the demo activity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conenor: integration of recycled fractions for new components formulation.. • Tomra: material sorting expertise • AIMPLAS: Validation of technology • FCBA: expertise in material recovery/ recycle material sampling
<p>What was the initial situation/problem preventing circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No technology for converting shredded FRP-feedstock into new sellable goods - Large volume of FRP from components reaching their EOL without a clear valorization route - Lack of sorting strategies and heterogenous recovered material streams - Inherent low value of the products/materials due to linear mindset and disposable products.
<p>What is being done in ECOBULK to solve the problem and enhance circularity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitating through the design more uniformed recovered material streams (design for disassembly, material traceability) (Conenor, Exergy, Lipor, FCBA) - Material and manufacturing technologies fostering the use of large recycled fractions (CONENOR) - Promoting the uptake of large recycled material fractions for applications with added value (CONENOR) - Reverse logistics through end-user platforms (material data base, QR identification, logistics platform, etc..) (ITENE) - Establishing synergies with other sectors for cross-sectorial impact - Reporting of barriers and opportunities to enhance circularity within material recovery
<p>How is it going to be demonstrated in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of large fractions of recycled materials in Ecobulk components up to and exceeding 90% in weight (Conenor). - Testing the assembly/disassembly strategies for products at the demsites for product and material recovery (Demosite responsables) - Testing recyclability of new and recycled components – (Conenor/CNR) - Establishing collaborations with other sectors for material sourcing (VIROL, Valdelia) and material valorisation (e.g Extruders and construction product providers) - Identification of circular business opportunities at the products' EoL at local scale. Case study in UK and Finland (OAK/CONENOR) - Promoting local networks for material/product recovery/reuse – Coventry/Warwickshire - Establishing the requirements, opportunities and barriers for (reverse) Logistics – WP8 (ITENE, Oakdene Hollins)
<p>What are the main innovations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing a valorisation route for high volume of thermoset FRP streams - Wood waste material recovery at high level 90%-w. for a second life cycle and thereafter (Conenor). - The use of circular thermoplastic composites for volume construction industry as an excellent route for boosting lower grade plastics

4.3.4. *Demonstration plans*

Specific timelines for the construction demo activities are presented below (Figures 37-42) considering each demo location (Finland, Portugal, France and the UK).

Conenor is acting in ECOBULK as an OEM, therefore most of the product recovery test will be performed in Finland, although the recyclability and structural characteristics tests will be performed also on panels from other demo locations after being exposed to different climate conditions. Other demo sites (Portugal, France, the UK) will play a role of living laboratories, serving as centres for the validation of the circular strategies through the installation of products, monitoring effects of their real-world use and collecting feedback from users and other stakeholders.

It is important to note that the proposed timelines in Figures 37-42 may be subject to modification matching with each demo site owner requests in due course, as well as the logistics information (such as the list of components/assemblies, quantities, timing, preliminary outline of activities and specific demo responsibilities) provided in complementary tables below the figures.

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CONENOR / KYMIRING / FINLAND

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	20 Modular shelter 50 Benches 1 or 2 Cabin shelter	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	SANKARI	09/18 - 05/20	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	On side by Kymiring
				Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	On side by Kymiring
Location	Kymiring MotoGP (Kausala)		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	05/19 - 05/20	Repair	Not likely		
Demo site timeframe	05/19-11/20		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	07/19 - 05/20	Recycling/downcycle	Päijät-Häme Waste Management Ltd (PHJ)		
Building permit required?	YES		Prototype responsibility	KYMIRING	07/19 - 08/20	Energy recovery	After remanufacturing by Lahti Energia		
Other requirements	Outdoor limited entry new construction site 1x6 km for MotoGP/event visitors at country side		Assembly responsibility	KYMIRING	08/19 & 08/20				
			Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	KYMIRING	08/19 & 08/20				
			Disassembly test	KYMIRING	At least 2 times				
			User acceptance test	CONENOR	During demo activity				

Figure 37: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Finland (Conenor/Kymiring)

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GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 Tree bench	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	INBICTA/LIPOR	until 04/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	Yes
		1 Drinking fountain		Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	Yes
		1 Recycling bin shelter		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	05/19 - 11/19		Repair	No
	Location	Adventure Park (Baguim do Monte)		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	07/19 - 11/19		Recycling/downcycle	Yes
	Demo site timeframe	09/19-11/20		Prototype responsibility	LIPOR	09/19 - 11/19			
	Building permit required?	NO		Assembly responsibility	LIPOR	09/19 - 11/20			
	Other requirements	Open entry existing recreational adventure park for visitors at country side		Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	LIPOR	09/19 - 11/20		Energy recovery	No
				Disassembly test	LIPOR	several times			
				User acceptance test	LIPOR	Continuous			

Figure 38: Timeline and logistics for the demo in Portugal (Lipor)

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GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 Table	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	FCBA	until 05/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	No
		1 Bench		Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	Yes
	Location	FCBA facilities (Bordeaux)		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	05/19 - 11/19		Repair	No
	Demo site timeframe	06/19-11/20		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	06/19 & 09/19		Recycling/downcycle	No
	Building permit required?	No		Prototype responsibility	FCBA	09/19 - 11/19			
	Other requirements	User experiences and perception at Sineugraff & Grossfillex		Assembly responsibility	FCBA	12/19 - 01/20		Energy recovery	No
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	FCBA	12/19 - 01/20			
				Disassembly test	FCBA	Sep-20			
		User acceptance test	FCBA	Sep-20					

Figure 39: Timeline and logistics for the demo in France (FCBA/Sineugraff & Grossfillex)

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WARWICK / UK - OUTDOOR FURNITURE

GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	2 Modular shelter	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	EXERGY	Until 09/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	through end user platform
	Location	Warwick University Campus		Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	within University
	Demo site timeframe	11/19-12/20		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	11/19 - 03/20		Repair	stakeholder platforms
	Building permit required?	No		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	11/19 & 03/20		Recycling/downcycle	No
	Other requirements			Prototype responsibility	WARWICK	11/19 - 12/20		Energy recovery	No
				Assembly responsibility	WARWICK	11/19 - 12/20			
		Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	WARWICK	11/19 - 12/20					
		Disassembly test	WARWICK	Several times, several tests					
		User acceptance test	WARWICK	During demo activity					

Figure 40: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Exergy/Warwick University)

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GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 Bike shelter	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	EXERGY	until 08/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	through end user platform
		2 Modular shelters		Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	within University
	Location	Coventry University Campus		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	12/19 - 02/20		Repair	stakeholder platforms
	Demo site timeframe	02/20-12/20		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	Feb-20		Recycling/downcycle	No
	Building permit required?	Yes		Prototype responsibility	COVENTRY	03/20 - 12/20		Energy recovery	No
	Other requirements			Assembly responsibility	COVENTRY	Mar-20			
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	COVENTRY	Mar-20			
Disassembly test			COVENTRY	several times					
		User acceptance test	COVENTRY	3 different times					

Figure 41: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Exergy/Coventry University)

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GENERAL INFO	Prototype information	1 modular shelter and some benches	PROTOTYPE CIRCULAR DESIGN	Design responsibility	EXERGY	Until 09/19	END OF LIFE ALTERNATIVES	Reuse	within University
	Location	Cranfield University Campus		Component materials sourcing	CONENOR	Continuous		Reassembly	within University
	Demo site timeframe	02/20-12/20		Prototype manufacture	CONENOR	12/19 - 03/20		Repair	No
	Building permit required?	YES/NO		Shipping responsibility	CONENOR	Mar-20			
	Other requirements			Prototype responsibility	CRANFIELD	03/20 - 11/20		Recycling/downcycle	No
				Assembly responsibility	CRANFIELD	Mar-20			
				Fixings (screws, L-shapes etc.)	CRANFIELD	Mar-20			
				Disassembly test	CRANFIELD	several times			
				User acceptance test	CRANFIELD	several times		Energy recovery	No

Figure 42: Timeline and logistics for the demo in the UK (Exergy/Cranfield University)

5. Conclusions and future work

During the period M12-M18 a common dialogue between the partners involved in demonstrations has been initiated in order to understand and establish the interactions between them for successful planning and outcome of the demonstration activities while understanding that the design process is iterative, with many cycles of prototyping, testing, analysing and refining a product and finally designing the user application in away to benefit of the properties and sustainability they provide. This dialogue has resulted an initial plan reported in M18 for several highly interesting large-scale demonstrations to become carried out all over Europe within this project.

Following the feedback received during the M18 project review meeting in Brussel, the project demonstrators have been reconsidered by taking the system approach and merging all elements of the circular economy set up that is being developed in ECOBULK (e.g. business models, end of life, take back systems, digital systems, etc.). The outcome of this work was the development of demonstration maps for all three sectors (furniture, construction and automotive), consisting of several demo activities at each stage of the circular value chain, and a list of partners involved in these demo activities. The maps are supported with the demo cards that summarise the baseline situation and the project value-added innovation enhancing circularity at each stage of the circular value chain.

The demo plans presented in M18 have been also updated with a more specific breakdown of demo activities, a list of key responsibilities for each demo site, logistics information and specific timelines for demos execution. It is important to note though that the demo plans and timelines shall not be considered as definite and could be subject to revision during their execution. This report is a live document which will be regularly updated as the demo activities advances.

Considering that the work in developing new circular design concepts in WP2 and new materials in WP3 is heading towards completion, the manufacturing process of ECOBULK components and products has already started. The next steps involve the coordination of the manufacturing processes with OEMs and the administrative procedures with the demo owners to make sure that the demo products are successfully deployed within the schedule. Also, the progress in other demo activities reported in the demo maps and cards will be monitored closely with responsible partners to ensure smooth execution and implementation of the demo plans. Any deviations from the predefined schedule will be regularly updated and contingency measures proposed.

Annex I Questionnaire template sent to demo site owners

Automotive demo site	Maier	CRF			MicroCab	
ECOBULK partner responsible for the demo	Maier (Gotzon Ugarte)	CRF (Enrico Mangino)			MicroCab (John Jostins and Anne Shepperd)	
ECOBULK automotive components	Fascia central console 					
1. About the demo site:						
1.1. How and where the pilot component(s) will be demonstrated/showcased in the ECOBULK project (e.g. permanent or temporary use, showrooms, exhibitions, fairs, internal component validation system, etc)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-industrial facilities for internal validation of processing systems. • Internal laboratory for validation tests on automotive components. • Workshops, showrooms and technical meetings with engineer and design teams of the Car Makers. 	CRF ECO-materials corner Ecomondo fair 2020/2021 FCA validation system	CRF ECO-materials corner Ecomondo fair 2020/2021 FCA validation system	Still TBD	We plan for a display of dashboard parts / materials / processes. This can be supported by explanatory graphics, posters, video to explain the processes that have been followed to design the products / source the materials and manufacture the parts for assembly. A Coventry based event which would allow for the Vianova (the new Left hand drive Microcab vehicle) to form part of the exhibition, allowing the parts to be displayed in situ. MC to discuss with Coventry University to identify possible venues.	Still TBD

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ECOBULK

1.2. How many components will have to be delivered for the demo activities? Please quantify in pieces, meters, other.	1 Ecobulk component (2K Injected Fascia) 20 injected sample parts (Fascia) per EcoBulk material 1 Assembly Tool (dashboard, radio, aerators, etc.)	At least 20 pieces	At least 20 pieces	Still TBD	We envisage 3-5 sets of dashboard parts will be manufactured.	3-5 sets
1.3. When do the components need to be delivered to the demo site?	Start of demonstration activities by M30 (Nov19) First delivery of injected components by M28 (Oct/19)	The mould will be available September 2019. As soon the material will be available, moulding trials will start.	The mould will be available September 2019. As soon the material will be available, moulding trials will start.	Still TBD	The parts need to be manufactured and installed into the vehicle before they are demonstrated. As the manufacturing process takes some time (design / tooling/ manufacture / assembly / installation) this needs to be programmed in. MC to arrange meetings with material suppliers (Coventive / others) re supply and also create a draft programme for manufacturing of parts	Still TBD
1.4 What would be the preliminary outline of activities to be completed at the demo site?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.- Manufacturing of the components (injection and paint of 2K Fascia sample parts) 2.- Validation tests of the components (according to functional specifications) 3.- Delivery of the Assembly Tool (Dasboard, Radio, Aerators, etc) 4.- Demonstrator installation at MTC 5.- Assembly/Disassembly Tests 6.- (Re-)manufacturing Tests 7.- EoLV Recovery Tests 					
2. Responsibilities						
2.1. Who is responsible for designing a) the assembly and b) the components?	Maier/MTC	CRF	CRF	CRF	MicroCab	MicroCab
2.2. Who is responsible for supplying materials for the components?	Maier/NetComposites/ Tecnaro	Coventive	Tecnaro	NTT/Technoplants	Coventive / Tecnaro	NTT/Technoplants

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2.3. Who is responsible for component manufacturing?	Maier/MTC	CRF	CRF	NTT/Technoplants	Third party	NTT/Technoplants
2.4. Who is responsible of component installation in the assembly?	Maier/MTC	CRF	CRF	CRF	MicroCab	MicroCab
2.5. Who is responsible for the installation(s) for demonstration(s) ?	Maier/MTC	CRF	CRF	CRF	MicroCab	MicroCab

Furniture demo site	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Warwick university and Coventry University	Moretti Compact showrooms	Lipor Adventure Park	Municipality in France (or FCBA in Bordeaux)	KymiRing MotoGP
ECOBULK partner responsible for the demo	TU Delft (Ruud Balkenende)	Cranfield University (Jose Endrino)	Exergy (Dominik Jasinski and Felipe Maya)	Moretti Compact (Giovanni Tosi and Francesco Balducci)	Lipor (Alexandre Ventura and Diana Nicolau)	FCBA (Alice Huchoncolunga)	Conenor (Markku Vilkki)
ECOBULK furniture products	Indoor furniture 						

1. About the demo site:

1.1. How and where the pilot component(s) will be demonstrated/showcased in the ECOBULK project (e.g. permanent or temporary use, showrooms, exhibitions, fairs, internal component validation system, etc)?	Study rooms in Industrial Design Engineering buildings	Study rooms for PhD students Furniture will be demonstrated in student dormitories	Two demo sites: Warwick University and Coventry University, both located in Coventry, UK. Furniture will be demonstrated in student dormitories.	3 showrooms: 1 Viale Oliveti, 1, - 47924 - Rimini - Italy 2 Via Luigi Einaudi, 61032 Fano - Italy 3 Via Giuseppe di Vittorio, 2, 61026 Piandimeleto - Italy Additional demo sites: COSMOB - Via della produzione,	Lipor's office buildings	Permanent use at Lipor Adventure Park Baguim do Monte, Portugal	Permanent use City of Bussy Saint George, France Alternatively, furniture sets could be installed the demo at FCBA facilities in Bordeaux.	KymiRing Moto GP track site 1x6km area under construction located at Kausala, Finland Positioning at the site shall be "where needed" and placing as many as possible at a central place
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ECOBULK

				61 – Montelabbate – Italy The fair “Salone del Mobile” in Milan				close to each other to gain momentum by visitors
1.2. How many components will have to be delivered for the demo activities? Please quantify in pieces, meters, other.	5 bookshelves 16 chairs	10 work stations >5 dormitory furniture sets (the exact number still to be agreed and decided in due time)	5-10 dormitory furniture sets per demo site, (the exact number still to be agreed and decided in due time) >5 bookshelves (still to be confirmed)	5 furniture sets	2 furniture sets, without the bed	alternative concepts under study / minimum 4 park benches	Maximum of 5 benches	50 Outdoor benches Info signs – to be decided
1.3. Are these products going to be installed permanently or temporarily?	Still to be confirmed	Still to be confirmed	Most likely permanently, but still to be confirmed	Permanently in showrooms and COSMOB, temporarily in the fair “Salone del Mobile” in Milan	The products will be installed permanently	The products will be installed permanently	Temporary installation, need to decommission at the end of the project	Permanently but removable to another chosen location at site
1.4. When do the components need to be delivered to the demo site?	Start of demonstration activities by M30 (Nov19)	Start of demonstration activities by M30 (Nov19)	Between M26 (July 2019)-M28 (September 2019), academic year in the UK starts in October and all dormitories needs to be fully furnished by that time	M28 (September 2019)	start M28 (September 2019)	start M28 (September 2019)	Specific timelines to be agreed, definitely start before M30 (November 2019)	Specific timeline still to be agreed with KymiRing, the first KymiRing Moto GP racing will not start until 2020, which is well aligned with ECOBULK
1.5 What would be the preliminary outline of activities to be completed at the demo site?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Delivery of components to the demo site 2. Final product assembly and installation 3. User experience-acceptance study 4. Upgrading/dissassembly test 5. Remanufacturing test 6. EoL recovery test 7. Dissemination activities <p>Detailed activities still to be agreed with the demo sites</p>							

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Responsibilities								
2.1. Who is responsible for designing a) the assembly and b) the components?	a) Moretti Compact b) Moretti Compact/KEAS/AkzoNobel	Lipor	Local municipal preference or Available designs from other partners (e.g. Kymiring or Lipor)	a) design of all product assemblies/installations and non-composite component responsibility by site architect company Sankari b) design of composite components responsibility by Conenor/Markku Vilkki				
2.2. Who is responsible for supplying materials for the components?	KEAS and AkzoNobel	sourcing of materials and supply of composite component responsibility by Conenor	sourcing of materials and supply of composite component responsibility by Conenor	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility by Site Owner KymiRing/Mr. Seppo Rossi b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite component responsibility by Conenor				
2.3. Who is responsible for component manufacturing?	KEAS and AkzoNobel	Conenor for composite components	Conenor for composite components	Conenor for composite components				
2.4. Who is responsible of component installation in the assembly?	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Exergy with possible help of demo site technicians	Moretti Compact	Lipor	Lipor	To be defined	Third party contractor to be chosen by KymiRing
2.5. Who is responsible for the installation(s) for demonstration(s)?	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Exergy with possible help of demo site technicians	Moretti Compact	Lipor	Lipor	To be defined	Third party contractor to be chosen by KymiRing

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Construction demo site	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Warwick university and Coventry University	Lipor Adventure Park	Municipality (France)	KymiRing MotoGP	
ECOBULK partner responsible for the demo	TU Delft (Ruud Balkenende)	Cranfield University (Jose Endrino)	Exergy (Dominik Jasinski and Felipe Maya)	Lipor (Alexandre Ventura and Diana Nicolau)	FCBA (Alice Huchoncolunga)	Conenor (Markku Vilkki)	
ECOBULK construction components	<p>Composite planks, panels, boards, pillars</p>						
Product Applications:	Multi-purpose convertible shelter for bikes, benches, waste bins	Multi-purpose convertible shelter for bikes, benches, waste bins	Multi-purpose convertible shelter for bikes, benches, waste bins	Picnic shelter Waste bin shelter Drinking fountain shelter	Bike shelter	Modular shelter Information cabin	
1. About the demo site:							
1.1. How and where the pilot component(s) will be demonstrated/showcased in the ECOBULK project (e.g. permanent or temporary use, showrooms, exhibitions, fairs, internal component validation system, etc)?	Pilots to be demonstrated at TuDelft still under discussion. Applications are being considered by the Architectural School and the exact locations are still to be agreed with the University Estate Managers	Pilots to be demonstrated at Cranfield University Campus. Exact locations are still to be agreed with the University Estate Managers	Pilots to be demonstrated with Warwick University and Coventry University in Coventry (UK). Final products will be installed at the University Campus areas, the exact locations are still to be agreed with the University Estate Managers.	Permanent use at Lipor Adventure Park Baguim do Monte, Portugal	Permanent use City of Bussy Saint George, France	KymiRing Moto GP track site 1x6km area under construction located at Kausala, Finland Permanent multiple COMPOSITE outdoor installations. Positioning at the site shall be "where needed" and placing as many as possible at a central place close to each other to gain momentum by visitors Non-woven textiles by NTT are under study for their applicability at info cabin internal wall covering	
1.2. How many components will have to be delivered for the demo activities?		- Bike shelters (1-2 units).	a) Warwick University:	alternative conceptual	1 bike shelter	Modular (open entry) Shelter 3x3m for people against rain,	

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ECOBULK

Please quantify in pieces, meters, other.			- Bike shelters (2-3 units) - Waste collection points (2-5 units) b) Coventry University: - bike shelters (2-3 units)	sketches under study to be decided large quantities		sun shine, etc. - 20 units Info Cabin / Information kiosk in metal frame with floor space and insulation material - 2 units
1.3. Are these products going to be installed permanently or temporarily?	Most likely permanently	Most likely permanently	Most likely permanently	Products will be installed permanently	Products will be installed permanently	Products will be installed permanently
1.4. When do the components need to be delivered to the demo site?	start M30 (November 2019) at the latest	start M30 (November 2019) at the latest	start M30 (November 2019) at the latest	start M30 (November 2019) at the latest	start M30 (November 2019) at the latest	Specific timeline still to be agreed with KymiRing, the first KymiRing Moto GP racing will not start until 2020, which is well aligned with ECOBULK timelines for demos, component deliveries from Conenor to start summer 2019
1.5. What would be the preliminary outline of activities to be completed at the demo site?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Delivery of components to the demo site 2. Final product assembly and installation 3. User experience-acceptance study 4. Upgrading/dissassembly test 5. Remanufacturing test 6. EoL recovery test 7. Dissemination activities <p>Detailed activities still to be agreed with the demo sites</p>					
2. Responsibilities						
2.1. Who is responsible for designing a) the assembly and b) the components?	a) Exergy b) Conenor	a) Exergy b) Conenor	a) Exergy b) Conenor	a) Lipor b) Conenor	a) Exergy/b) Conenor	a) demo site architect company Sankari b) Conenor and (?) NTT
2.2. Who is responsible for supplying materials for the components?	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility of TU Delft b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite components responsibility by Conenor	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility of Cranfield University b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite components responsibility by	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility of Exergy b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite component responsibility of Conenor	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility of Lipor b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite components responsibility by Conenor	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility of FCBA b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite components responsibility by Conenor	a) supply of all non-composite materials responsibility by Site Owner KymiRing b) sourcing of materials and supply of composite components responsibility by Conenor and (?) non-wovens NTT

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		Conenor				
2.3. Who is responsible for component manufacturing?	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers	Composite components - Conenor, other components - external suppliers, non-wovens (?) NTT
2.4. Who is responsible of component installation in the assembly?	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Exergy with support of demo site technicians	Lipor	To be defined	Third party contractor to be chosen by site owner KymiRing
2.5. Who is responsible for the installation(s) for demonstration(s) ?	TU Delft	Cranfield University	Exergy with support of demo site technicians	Lipor	To be defined	Third party contractor to be chosen by site owner KymiRing